

**IN THE FORM OF AN UNBOUNDED PARALLELEPIPED IN THE
FIELD NONLOCAL BORDERLINE CONDITIONAL LINEAR THE
REVERSE IS THE CASE.**

Sharipova Madina Pulatovna

Asia International University

General technician Department of Sciences teacher

saripovamadina807.m@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10521409>

ANNOTATION.

(management issues) have been studied.

Key words : Correct and incorrect issues seminolocal , Laplace operator , Fourier replacement , a priori evaluation .

ANNOTATION.

In the article, in the process of studying non-local issues, it is studied that they are closely related to the opposite issues (management issues)
Enter

In the process of studying non-local issues, it was found that they are closely related to inverse issues (management issues). In the theory of differential equations, such problems are called inverse problems, in which, along with determining the solution of the differential equation, the problem of determining the coefficients or the right side (external force) of the equation is understood.

The interest in studying inverse problems for mathematical physics equations is explained by the importance of their application in various fields of mechanics, seismology, medical tomography, and geophysics.

This is the relevance of our research work defines.

This

$$G = (0,1) \times (0,T) \times R = Q \times R = \{(x,t,z); x \in (0,1), 0 < t < T < +\infty, z \in R\}$$

in the field the following the equation let's see :

$$Lu = u_t - \Delta u + c(x,t)u = f(x,t,z), \tag{1}$$

this on the ground $\Delta u = u_{xx} + u_{zz}$ — Laplace operator .

Suppose in equation (2.1). $c(x,t)$ coefficient Q in the field enough smooth function let it be

Semi-local boundary issue.

This

$$\gamma u|_{t=0} = u|_{t=T}, \tag{2}$$

$$u|_{x=0} = u|_{x=1} = 0, \tag{3}$$

seminolocal borderline conditions , and

$$\lim_{|z| \rightarrow \infty} u = 0, \lim_{|z| \rightarrow \infty} u_z = 0 \tag{4}$$

conditions of satisfying equation (2.1). $W_{2,x,t,z}^{2,1,3}(G)$ in space generalized find the solution . Here γ – something is a fixed number , the value of below is determined .

Definition 1.1. (1)-4) of the problem generalized as a solution to equation (1). and (2)-(3) conditions almost everyone in the place satisfactory and (4) the executor $u(x,t,z) \in W_2^{2,1,3}(G)$ to the function we say

Here $W_2^{2,1,3}(G) = W_{2,x,t,z}^{2,1,3}(G)$ through

$$\|u\|_{W_2^{2,1,3}(G)} = (2\pi)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (1+|\lambda|^2)^3 \|\hat{u}\|_{W_2^{2,1}(Q)}^2 d\lambda$$

the norm with given Hilbert spaces [18,21,29] are defined being , this space elements for $u, u_t, u_x, u_{xx}, u_{zz} \in L_2(G)$ appropriate will be , from this except $W_{2,x,t}^{2,1}(Q)$ through

$$\|u\|_{W_2^{2,1}(Q)}^2 = \int_Q (u^2 + u_t^2 + u_x^2 + u_{xx}^2) dQ$$

to the norm have Sobolev spaces defined . Here all derivatives generalized in a sense is being taken and $\hat{u}$ expression $u(x,t,z)$ of the function z variable according to Fourier represents the substitution [4,31] :

$$\hat{u}(x,t,\lambda) = (2\pi)^{-1/2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} u(x,t,z) e^{-i\lambda z} dz.$$

In the future c_i through positive , in general when from each other honorable different from scratch different immutable numbers let's define .

Theorem 1.1. We assume $c(x,t)$ coefficient for the following conditions

done be : $\mu c(x,t) - c_t(x,t) \geq \delta_1 > 0$ all $(x,t) \in \bar{Q}$, this earth a $\mu = \frac{2}{T} \ln |\gamma| > 0, |\gamma| > 1$,

all $x \in [0,1]$ for , $c(x,T) = c(x,0)$ let it be In that case optional $f \in W_2^{1,1,3}(G)$ function for (1)-(4) of the problem $W_2^{2,1,3}(G)$ is the only generalization in space the solution there is will be **Fourier replacement using harvest done helper issue solving** _

For problem (1)-(4). Fourier replacement supporting $Q = (0,1) \times (0,T)$ in the field the following issue we get :

$$L\hat{u} = \hat{u}_t - \hat{u}_{xx} + (c(x,t) + \lambda^2)\hat{u} = \hat{f}(t, x, z), \tag{5}$$

$$\gamma\hat{u}|_{t=0} = \hat{u}|_{t=T}, \tag{6}$$

$$\hat{u}|_{x=0} = \hat{u}|_{x=1} = 0. \tag{7}$$

Definition 1.2. (5)-(7) of the problem generalized as a solution to equation (4). almost everyone on the ground and conditions (6), (7). satisfactory $\hat{u}(x,t,\lambda) \in W_2^{2,1}(Q)$ to the function it is said.

Theorem 1.2. *Ayatlylik of Theorem 1.1 everyone conditions done let it be In that case optional $\hat{f}(x,t,\lambda) \in L_2(Q)$ function for (5)-(7) of the problem $W_2^{2,1}(Q)$ unique solution in space there is will be*

(5)-(7) of the problem solution integral energy of unity using proof we do

We assume that (5)-(7) of the problem the solution $W_2^{2,1}(Q)$ available at let it be

This

$$2(L\hat{u}, e^{-\mu t}\hat{u}_t)_0 = 2(\hat{f}, e^{-\mu t}\hat{u}_t)_0$$

the moment let 's see on the ground $\mu = const > 0$.

By the conditions of Theorem 1.2 according to (7) ainiyat in pieces integrally, the following inequality easy cause release can :

$$\|\hat{u}\|_{W_2^1(Q)}^2 \leq c_1 \|\hat{f}\|_Q^2. \tag{2.8}$$

For real too, initially

$$2(L\hat{u}, e^{-\mu t}\hat{u}_t)_0 \geq 2\|\hat{u}_t\|_0^2 + \lambda\|\hat{u}_x\|_0^2 + \delta_1\|\hat{u}\|_0^2$$

that we will prove. This

$$(\hat{u}_t - \hat{u}_{xx} + (c(x,t) + \lambda^2)\hat{u}, e^{-\mu t}\hat{u}_t) = (\hat{f}, e^{-\mu t}\hat{u}_t)$$

the moment let's look. In that case

$$1) 2(\hat{u}_t, e^{-\mu t}\hat{u}_t) = 2 \int_Q (\hat{u}_t)^2 e^{-\mu t} dt dx$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2) -2(\hat{u}_{xx}, e^{-\mu t}\hat{u}_t) &= -2 \int_Q \hat{u}_{xx} e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_t dt dx = 2 \int_Q \hat{u}_x \hat{u}_{tx} e^{-\mu t} dt dx - 2 \int_{\partial Q} e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_t \hat{u}_x \nu_x dS = \\ &= \int_Q e^{-\lambda t} (\hat{u}_x^2)_t dt dx = \lambda \int_Q e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_x^2 dt dx + \int_{\partial Q} e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_x^2 \nu_x dS \end{aligned}$$

this on the ground ν expression ∂Q to the border transferred normal, dS element unit.

$$\begin{aligned}
 3) 2(c\hat{u}, e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_t) &= 2 \int_Q c \hat{u}_t e^{-\mu t} dQ = \int_Q c (\hat{u}^2)'_t e^{-\mu t} dQ = \\
 &= \int_Q (\lambda c - c_t) e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}^2 dQ + \int_{\partial Q} e^{-\mu t} c \hat{u}^2 \nu_t dS. \\
 2(c\hat{u}, e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_t) &\geq \delta_1 \int_Q e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}^2 dQ
 \end{aligned}$$

this from the ground

$$\|\hat{u}\|_{W_2^1(Q)}^2 \leq c_1 \|\hat{f}\|_{L_2(Q)}^2 \quad (8)$$

this on the ground $c_1 = \frac{1}{\sigma}$, $\sigma = \min\{e^{-\mu T}, \lambda e^{-\mu T}, \delta_1 e^{-\mu T}\}$, from problem (4)-(6).

$W_2^1(Q_1)$ the uniqueness of come comes out

$\hat{u}_{xx} \in L(Q)$ that we will show . Of this for again the following a priori from assessment we use :

$$\left| -2 \int_Q L \hat{u} e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_{xx} dx dt \right| = \left| -2 \int_Q \hat{f} e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_{xx} dx dt \right|.$$

From below and from above evaluations we can get from below let's start :

$$1) -2 \int_Q \hat{u}_t e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_{xx} dx dt = \mu \|\hat{u}_x\|^2;$$

$$2) 2 \int_Q \hat{u}_{xx} e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_{xx} dx dt \geq \frac{2}{e^{\mu T}} \int_Q \hat{u}_{xx}^2 dx dt = \frac{2}{e^{\mu T}} \|\hat{u}_{xx}\|_0^2)$$

$$3) -2 \int_Q c \hat{u} e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_{xx} dx dt \geq -2\varepsilon \int_Q e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_{xx}^2 dx dt - \frac{2\|c\|_{C(Q)}^2}{\varepsilon} \int_Q \hat{u}^2 dx dt \geq -\frac{2\varepsilon}{e^{\mu T}} \|\hat{u}_{xx}\|_0^2 - \frac{2\|c\|_{C(Q)}^2}{\varepsilon} \|\hat{u}\|_0^2)$$

$$4) -2\lambda^2 \int_Q \hat{u} \hat{u}_{xx} dx dt = 2\lambda^2 \int_Q (\hat{u}_x)^2 dx dt = 2\lambda^2 \|\hat{u}_x\|_0^2)$$

Now from above evaluations we get :

5)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left| -2 \int_Q \hat{f} \hat{u}_{xx} e^{-\mu t} dx dt \right| &= 2 \left| \int_Q \hat{f} \hat{u}_{xx} e^{-\mu t} dx dt \right| \leq 2 \int_Q |\hat{f} \hat{u}_{xx} e^{-\mu t}| dx dt \leq \frac{2}{\varepsilon} \int_Q \hat{f}^2 dx dt + 2\varepsilon \int_Q e^{-\mu t} \hat{u}_{xx}^2 dx dt \leq \\
 &\leq \frac{2}{\varepsilon} \|\hat{f}\|_0^2 + 2\varepsilon \|\hat{u}_{xx}\|_0^2;
 \end{aligned}$$

inequality in consideration take

$$\frac{2}{e^{\mu T}} \|\hat{u}_{xx}\|_0^2 - \frac{2\varepsilon}{e^{\mu T}} \|\hat{u}_{xx}\|_0^2 - 2\varepsilon \|\hat{u}_{xx}\|_0^2 \leq \frac{2}{\varepsilon} \|\hat{f}\|_0^2 + \frac{2\|c\|_{C(Q)}^2}{\varepsilon} \|\hat{u}\|_0^2,$$

$$\left(\frac{2}{e^{\mu T}} - \frac{2\varepsilon}{e^{\mu T}} - 2\varepsilon \right) \|\hat{u}_{xx}\|_0^2 \leq \frac{2}{\varepsilon} \|\hat{f}\|_0^2 + \frac{2\|c\|_{C(Q)}^2}{\varepsilon} \|\hat{u}\|_0^2 \leq \frac{2}{\varepsilon} \|\hat{f}\|_0^2 + \frac{2c_1\|c\|_{C(Q)}^2}{\varepsilon} \|f\|_0^2.$$

ε the choose at the expense of $\left(\frac{2}{e^{\mu T}} - \frac{2\varepsilon}{e^{\mu T}} - 2\varepsilon \right) > \varepsilon_0 > 0$ by doing get can _

$$\|\hat{u}_{xx}\|_0^2 \leq \left(\frac{2}{\varepsilon\varepsilon_0} + \frac{2c_1\|c\|_{C(Q)}^2}{\varepsilon\varepsilon_0} \right) \|f\|_0^2. \quad (9)$$

(9) from inequality $\hat{u}_{xx} \in L(Q)$ come comes out (2.8) into inequality (2.9). if we add , it is necessary assessment we can

$$\|\hat{u}\|_{W_2^{2,1}(Q)}^2 \leq c_2 \|\hat{f}\|_{L_2(Q)}^2. \quad (10)$$

References:

1. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 360-365.
2. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 137-141.
3. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 135-138.
4. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. International journal of sciearchers, 2(2), 101-103.
5. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 245-248.
6. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 102-110.
7. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66).
8. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 106-113.
9. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 115-121.
10. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 50-56.

11. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 420–424.
12. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 425–429.
13. Sharipova, M. P. (2024). ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 525–532.
14. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 368-372.
15. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. Development and innovations in science, 2(11), 29-35.
16. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.
17. Zulxumor, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA, 1(6), 128-132.
18. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) STATISTICAL PACKAGES OF CAPABILITIES. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(12), 781-787.
19. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) CAPABILITIES OF THE STATISTICAL DATABASE LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 274-280.
20. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 120-128.
21. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ELECTRONIC EDUCATION: TASKS AND OPPORTUNITIES. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 171-177.
22. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 99-109.
23. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 113-120.

24. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). Programming Environments for Creating Mobile Applications on the Android Operating System. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 305-309.
25. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). CAPUTO MA'NOSIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TO'G'RI MASALALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 375-382.
26. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). BETA FUNKSIYA XOSSALARI VA BU FUNKSIYA YORDAMIDA TURLI MASALALARNI YECHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 66-76.
27. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). KASR TARTIBLI ODDIY DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 383-390.
28. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). GAMMA FUNKSIYA. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 391-399.
29. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
30. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 1(10), 13-23.
31. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
32. daughter Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. World of Scientific news in Science, 1(2), 163-176.
33. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In " Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
34. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 216-220.
35. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG-LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 238-244.
36. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. SCHOLAR, 1(31), 263-269.
37. Boboqulova, M. X. (2023). STOMATOLOGIK MATERIALLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 223-228.

38. Xamroyevna, B. M. (2023). ORGANIZM TO 'QIMALARINING ZICHLIGINI ANIQLASH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 50-58.
39. Khamroyevna, M. B. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES, BIOPHYSICAL MECHANISMS OF MOVEMENT OF SUBSTANCES IN THE MEMBRANE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 217-221.
40. Bobokulova, M. K. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF FIBER OPTIC DEVICES IN MEDICINE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 212-216.
41. Mukhtaram Bobokulova Khamroyevna. (2023). Radiation Protection. Dosimetry . Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(6), 134-139.
42. Bobokulova, M. K. (2024). TOLALI OPTIKA ASBOBLARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 517-524.
43. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo'llash usul va vositalari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 481-486.
44. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.
45. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201.
46. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.
47. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
48. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
49. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).
50. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
51. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).

52. Quvvatov, B. U. o'g'li . (2023). ALEXNET - TASVIRLARNI TASNIFLASH UCHUN KONVOLYUTION NEYRON TARMOQ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 77–90.
53. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g'li Quvvatov. (2023). MAXIMUM PRINCIPLE AND ERROR ANALYSIS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 480–486.
54. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). RSA VA EL-GAMAL OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDA ELEKTRON RAQMLI IMZOLARI. RSA OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDAGI ELEKTRON RAQAMLI IMZO. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 316-319.
55. Sharopova, M. M. qizi . (2023). JAVA TILI YORDAMIDA OB'EKTGA YUNALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH ASOSLARI BILAN TANISHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 111–119.
56. Sharopova, M. (2023). CHOOSE: COMPOSITION OR INHERITANCE. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 96-102.
57. Sharopova, M. (2023). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE HERITAGE TO DO SYNTAX. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 82-87.
58. Sharopova, M. (2023). ARRAY AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 2(12), 102-107.
59. Sharopova, M. (2023). CLASSES AGAIN APPLY. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 106-111.
60. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). INTRODUCING" PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 222-231.
61. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 232-236.
62. Sharopova, M. (2024). DSA ERI STANDARD. ELECTRONIC DIGITAL SIGNATURE OF GOST R 34.10-94. B THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 169–178).
63. Sharopova, M. (2024). ELECTRONIC DIGITAL SIGNATURE ALGORITHMS BASED ON THE COMPLEXITY OF THE FACTORIZATION PROBLEM. B SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 66–74).
64. Sharopova, M. (2024). ARRAYS AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. B CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 102–110).

65. Sharopova, M. (2024). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE FLOWING INPUT AND RELEASE. В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
66. Sharopova, M. (2024). COLLECTORS. (OBJECT CONTAINERS). В DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 93–101).
67. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED SYSTEM FOR CONTROLLING TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY IN PRODUCTION ROOMS. В DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
68. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. В ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 16–27).
69. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. В MODELS AND METHODS IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
70. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. В INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 54–63).
71. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. В МЕЖДУРОДНАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ АКАДЕМИЧЕСКИХ НАУК (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 46–55).
72. Tursunov, B. J., & Allazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. Theory and practice of contemporary science, 3(45), 305-308.
73. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. Теория и практика современной науки, (3 (45)), 305-308.
74. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 296-304.
75. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(10), 108-117.

76. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 288-293.
77. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 280-287.
78. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.
79. Ахмедова, О. Б., Турсунов, Б. Ж., & угли Худойбердиев, Н. Н. (2022). Анализ физико-химических свойств нефтешламов Бухарского НПЗ и рациональные способы их утилизации. Science and Education, 3(6), 495-507.
80. Турсунов, Б. Д. (2016). Анализ и выявление путей совершенствования процессов горного дела. Молодой ученый, (23), 105-106.
81. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). СОЗДАНИЕ ПРОГРАММЫ ДЛЯ ИМИТАЦИИ ШИФРОВАНИЯ МАШИНЫ ENIGMA НА ЯЗЫКЕ PYTHON. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 317-323.
82. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). STUDY THE PSYCHOLOGY OF PROGRAMMERS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 563-568.
83. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). THE MAIN SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DEPARTMENTS OF PHYSICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.
84. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). RELATIONSHIPS OF PHYSICS WITH ART IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.
85. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). ADVANCED STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING PHYSICS. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.
86. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 157-161.
87. Jurakulov, S. (2023). PROPERTIES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF NUCLEAR ENERGY. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 35-39.
88. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Hamidov, E. (2023). YADRO ENERGIYASINING XOSSA VA XUSUSIYATLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 182-186.
89. IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION
90. SZ Jurakulov, O Nurboyev - GOLDEN BRAIN, 2023

91. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). FIZIKA FANINI O 'RGANISHNING YUQORI DARAJADAGI STRATEGIYALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.
92. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). TA'LIM SOHASIDA FIZIKANING SAN'AT BILAN ALOQALARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.
93. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). FIZIKA FANINING BO 'LIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHDAGIDAGI ASOSIY AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.
94. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 9-20.
95. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 9-20.
96. Jurakulov, S. (2023). IMPACT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY ON PEOPLE AND THE ENVIRONMENT. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 143-150.
97. Jurakulov, S. (2023). CHANGES IN LANGUAGE DUE TO NEW PHYSICS. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 77-87.

